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Strengthening the supervision mechanism of Medical Officer of Health areas under Regional Director of Health Services Colombo, Sri Lanka

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Background: Medical officer of health (MOH) offices deliver a vast range of services. Regular and comprehensive supervision of these services by supervisory officers is crucial to ensure timeliness, accuracy and quality of service.

Description of the intervention/ initiative: A strategy was planned to strengthen the district supervision methodology. From 2025 all completed supervision reports were collected monthly from each MOH and evaluated at district level. At the end of each month new formats for the ensuing month and evaluated supervisions from the previous month were delivered to the MOH office accompanied by an official written communication acknowledging the number of supervision reports forwarded. MOH offices were given access to view a database which identified each supervisory officer by name and designation with the number of supervisions submitted. Progress of reporting was displayed at supervisory officers' meetings. Key observations were communicated duly via online meetings.

Methods used for the evaluation: Medical officers and the public health nursing sister should complete six supervisions per month while supervising public health inspector and supervising public health midwife should complete ten. All supervision reports submitted on the last day of each month were considered timely while their completeness was evaluated at district level.

Results: Out of 18 MOHs 16 showed an increase in the supervision report submission rates. The district value showed an increase from 50% to 62 % from January to February. In January 9 MOHs achieved a submission rate $\geq 50\%$ while 13 achieved $\geq 50\%$ in February.

Lessons learnt: Transparent monitoring systems improve quality of supervisions and thus potentially improve overall performance of services delivered by MOH offices

Keywords: Supervision, Medical officer of health

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